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ENABLING PHYSICAL INTERNET INFORMATION SYSTEM – TRENDS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- INTRODUCTION 3
- 1. BACKGROUND 4
 - 1.1. ICT AND MULTIMODAL TRANSPORTATION 4
 - 1.2. BACKGROUND OF PHYSICAL INTERNET 5
 - 1.3. PROBLEM DEFINITION 5
- 2. METHODOLOGY 7
- 3. DISCUSSION..... 9
 - 3.1. OVERVIEW..... 9
 - 3.2. UNDERSTANDING THE FEATURES OF PI INFORMATION SYSTEM 11
 - 3.3. COMPARING TO CONVENTIONAL LOGISTICS INFORMATION SYSTEM 12
 - 3.4. GAPS AND FUTURE TRENDS 14
- 4. CONCLUSION..... 17
- REFERENCES..... 18
- ANNEXE 1. THE LIST OF REVIEWED PAPERS 23

INTRODUCTION

Physical Internet (PI) is an emerging logistics and supply chain management paradigm. PI takes advantage of extensive interconnectivity to reform the operations. The information system is the backbone to support the activities in this novel paradigm. In this review paper, we aim to investigate the state-of-the-art and research gaps in the PI information system. We focus on the distinctive features of the PI information system and make comparisons with general logistics research regarding the research trends. Finally, we identify some directions of the PI information system for future research.

1. BACKGROUND

In this article, we investigate the state-of-the-art of information system research regarding a logistics concept named Physical Internet (PI). PI proposes a novel paradigm that reforms the operations in every aspect of the supply chain, taking advantage of the wide application of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and the consequent interconnectivity. As a novel concept, PI was only formally introduced in the 2010s for the first time (Pan *et al.*, 2017). PI information system research, a fundamental component of PI, thus also remains in an early stage. This review will focus on PI information system research to provide up-to-date and practical insights for future research.

1.1. ICT AND MULTIMODAL TRANSPORTATION

ICT infrastructure has become one of the essential performance indicators for supply chains (Maestrini *et al.*, 2017). Logistics research also increasingly stresses the interconnectivity of information systems among organisations, which enables more efficient, flexible and sustainable operations. Multimodal transport connects different modes of transportation to fulfil some previously impossible transportation tasks. It also provides the potential to hand over cargo from trucks to more sustainable means.

In order to move towards efficient and sustainable logistics, multimodal transport has been evolving into many variants, such as intermodal, co-modal and synchronomodal transport. Their definitions and distinctions are given in Steadieseifi *et al.* (2014). The initial improvement aspects are in the planning stage to ensure the best transport options are chosen. Whereas in synchronomodal transport, the enabling requirements are threefold: integrated, real-time and flexible planning (van Riessen *et al.*, 2015). Pfoser *et al.* (2022) also analysed the three mechanisms, in which information systems function as essential support. Thus, ICTs are increasingly stressed along with the evolution, especially in synchronomodal transport. De Juncker *et al.* (2018) perform a simulation to demonstrate the importance of information availability in synchronomodal transport. The control tower is a well-studied ICT architecture solution for synchronomodal transport. For example, Hofman (2014) and Mes and Iacob (2016). Bol Raap *et al.* (2016) propose an integration platform for 4PLs (fourth-party logistics service providers) with a common data architecture to connect very heterogeneous ICT infrastructures. Bartoletti and Pompianu (2017) study the use case of the smart contract from blockchain in synchronomodal transport for trust and security needs.

1.2. BACKGROUND OF PHYSICAL INTERNET

PI envisions operating cargo in the same way as how data is processed in digital Internet (DI). Therefore, PI entails extensive interconnection among the network for visibility and real-time operations. In Montreuil (2011), the foundation of PI is designed, calling for more inspiration from DI. In PI, the PI containers are the minimum operating unit varying in size. They encapsulate cargo or other PI containers to be transported through the smart network. To build a smart network, the design expects the existing vehicles, hubs, etc., to transit to a more interconnected and intelligent PI counterpart. PI is defined as: “an open global logistics system founded on physical, digital and operational interconnectivity through encapsulation, interfaces and protocols” (Montreuil *et al.*, 2013). Thus, an information system is essential for such a network.

Treiblmaier *et al.* (2020) categorise PI research into three stages: the incubation stage (2008-2011), the exploration stage (2012-2014) and the expansion stage (2015-the article publication). Research in the incubation stage is mainly non-journal articles focusing on completing the design of PI (e.g., Montreuil *et al.* (2010) and Montreuil (2011)). In the exploration stage, many studies began to validate and assess the PI concepts. Lin *et al.* (2014) investigate the design of PI containers and evaluate the utilisation rate. Sarraj *et al.* (2014) conduct a simulation for a multimodal transport network with different levels of PI settings to assess the efficiency of PI. It is since the expansion stage that we found journal articles about the PI information system, along with various cases and assessment studies on application scenarios of PI. There is research on topics other than information systems, for example, road-rail PI hub scheduling (Walha *et al.*, 2016), inventory management (Pan *et al.*, 2015; Yang *et al.*, 2017), pricing models (Qiao *et al.*, 2020), etc.

1.3. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Conceptually, the foundation of PI has been well-defined (Montreuil, 2011; Montreuil *et al.*, 2013). An open logistics interconnection (OLI) model is proposed, learning from its counterparts in DI (Montreuil *et al.*, 2012). While in real-life applications, the architecture of PI information systems can vary.

Intuitively, centralisation naturally arises as the solution to the lack of visibility of the network, which is also the design for synchromodal transport. However, PI shows a decentralisation nature, although the research of the two concepts generally started at the same time (Ambra *et al.*, 2019). This decentralisation tendency of PI can be clearly observed in the information system design.

As a novel logistics paradigm, PI can also have other unique features. The resulting design of information systems can also reflect the practical challenges dealt with in PI. By examining

how data is managed and how information systems are designed, this review will provide insights into the distinctive features of PI information systems, like decentralisation, and why PI information systems are designed this way as compared to conventional paradigms. These discussions will hopefully further reveal the obstacles and future trends in PI research.

Therefore, we raise the following research questions (RQs) to be answered in this review.

- *RQ1: What are the characteristics of the PI information system?*
- *RQ2: Does the development of information systems of PI share the same features as general transport research?*
- *RQ3: What are the research gaps for PI information systems?*

The following sections will reflect the research questions. Section 2 explains the methodology used for collecting and analysing the data. Section 3 presents the findings and addresses the RQs through the review. Finally, Section 4 summarises the findings and concludes the article.

2. METHODOLOGY

We confine our scope to the research on the PI information system. This includes not only the design of PI information systems but also the ideas that relate to managing the data in PI, such as information architectures, data-sharing standards, and layered frameworks.

We only focus on journal articles to ensure the quality and completeness of the research. The journals are credible and peer-viewed that are recorded in CiteScore Matrix. We first used the keyword “Physical Internet” to search on Scopus. The search can find articles on irrelevant topics (e.g., Internet infrastructure), which are to be filtered out. Since the first journal article of PI was published in 2011 (Montreuil, 2011), the search span is set from 2011 to October 2022 (the time of this work).

For every relevant paper, we confine the scope to research with a focus on the information system, frameworks and architectures. As inclusive criteria, if the paper applies the idea of PI for such designs, or explores the development of PI in these aspects, it is considered relevant for this review. On the other hand, papers are excluded from the scope if PI is only mentioned in the literature review section or as a potential topic for future research therein. We define this by reading the articles and distinguishing their themes. This returns 19 papers. Then, a further search on Google Scholar is conducted. Applying the same inclusive and exclusive criteria, 9 additional articles are collected, which results in 28 papers in total for this review.

A list of the reviewed papers can be found in Annex 1. Initial analysis and categorisation are conducted as well while reading the papers. First, we summarise the Practical Problem, Conceptual Problem and Outcome/Contribution. Practical Problem refers to the empirical issue that the paper solves, while Conceptual Problem is how the paper treats the problem in their models or methods. Outcome/Contribution outlines the solution and conceptual contribution of the reviewed paper. Then the Problem Scope is categorised as 0 – general, 1 – single facility, 2 – connecting logistics, 3 – local area network (LAN) and 4 - network. It should be clarified here that we define LAN as a confined area, usually with a distinct central facility to be served, while Network refers to larger areas that contain multiple LANs in a more general way. A demonstration of the classification of the problem scope is in Figure 1. The Application Theme is also summed up to show the cases studied in the reviewed paper.

Figure 1. Classification of the problem scope

According to Pan *et al.* (2017) and Treiblmaier *et al.* (2020), the PI articles can be categorised into *conceptual research*, *assessment research*, *solution design research*, *validation research* and *literature research*. This categorisation is recorded as the Research Type of the reviewed paper. Next, we mark the technologies used in the solution proposed and denoted by the Enabling Technologies. In the end, we examine why the paper uses PI and how PI is understood in the paper.

3. DISCUSSION

In this section, we first present an overview of the findings in the literature in Section 3.1. Then the RQs are answered respectively through the discussions in the following subsections.

3.1. OVERVIEW

A summarisation of the level of scope of the reviewed paper is presented in Figure 2. There is a cluster of research that devise solutions based on PI for very specific use cases (level 1), especially in the early stage. Qiu *et al.* (2015) build a service-oriented architecture (SoA) for the interconnection of physical assets in a Supply Hub in Industrial Park (SHIP). Zhong *et al.* (2016) propose a PI-enabled Manufacturing Executive System for an intelligent workshop to lower error rates and acquire timely information. For similar reasons, Chen *et al.* (2018) develop a PI-enabled Building Information Modelling System for prefabricated construction, and Lin and Cheng (2018) implement PI into systems for a solar energy manufacturer in a case study. Zhong *et al.* (2017) employ IoT devices on a shop floor to convert logistics resources into smart manufacturing objects so as to gain visibility through big data analysis.

Figure 2. Overview of the problem scope of the reviewed papers

More recent papers tend to broaden the application scenarios or their problem scope than design a dedicated solution. Kubek and Więcek (2019) combine PI with city logistics and create a framework for a decision support system based on the OLI model of PI. Tan *et al.* (2021) propose a reverse Vickery auction as the pricing model for a shared parking space upon presenting a framework for a PI parking management system. Fahim *et al.* (2021a) analyse the

new role and position of seaports in PI. In another work, Fahim *et al.* (2021b) design an information architecture for seaports to enable track and trace. This is also the first time that seaports are specifically considered in PI, as such a complex system entails a great number of reconfigurations. Leung *et al.* (2022) present a synchronisation framework for warehouse management as the first model to address the operations in a PI node.

The majority of the remaining papers are conceptual research and are associated with technologies and concepts from other fields. Hofman *et al.* (2016) introduce semantic technology as a key enabler for data sharing and, thus, various optimisations. Maslarić *et al.* (2016) compare PI and Industry 4.0 and propose PI as a potential realisation of Industrial 4.0 in the logistics sector. Sallez *et al.* (2016) define the concept of product activeness and introduce a framework for PI container holon. Wang *et al.* (2016) also exploit the activeness of individual machines and propose the idea of initiative scheduling in a manufacturing environment. Pujo and Ounnar (2018) propose a cyber-physical logistic system for PI under a holonic paradigm. Gumzej (2022) brings the idea of the intelligent logistics system (iLS) into PI and devises the ontology. Tran-Dang and Kim (2021) refer to digital transformation and new technologies as a trend towards Industry 4.0 and summarise the perspectives and challenges of PI.

IoT is found to be a crucial underpinning technology of PI. Pal and Kant (2018) stress the importance of sensing devices in PI and especially for fresh food logistics. An IoT-based architecture is proposed by Tran-Dang and Kim (2018) in line with the initial design of Montreuil *et al.* (2010). Tran-Dang *et al.* (2020a) review the application and challenges of IoT in logistics in general. Tran-Dang *et al.* (2020b) focus on the application of IoT in PI and present prototypes to build a PI-IoT eco-system composed of smart objects, smart PI management systems and smart networks.

Blockchain is also studied in the context of PI to address trust issues (Betti *et al.*, 2019) and facilitate the decentralisation aspect of PI (Meyer *et al.*, 2019). Hasan *et al.* (2021) implement two blockchain architectures in PI and justify their practicality.

Researchers also envision the smart Product Service System (PSS) as an appropriate framework for the PI system design. Zhang *et al.* (2016) conduct a simulation of sustainable logistics within an architecture of PSS with smart boxes. Pan *et al.* (2019) present smart PSS as an important building block for the implementation of PI.

There is also an idea of the Internet of Perishable Logistics (IoPL) with layered architecture proposed by Kant and Pal (2017) as a special application scenario of PI. The architecture is further elaborated on and evaluated by Pal and Kant (2019).

3.2. UNDERSTANDING THE FEATURES OF PI INFORMATION SYSTEM

In the above-mentioned definition of PI, the core feature stressed is interconnectivity. This is acknowledged by most of the papers. Especially for the studies with dedicated use cases in the early stage, interconnectivity is the sole understanding and contribution of PI. IoT devices are deployed to acquire data from cargo which are further managed in a centralised system. According to the idea of activeness proposed by Sallez *et al.* (2016), such IoT devices perform class 1 and 2 intelligence, that is, information handling intelligence and problem notification intelligence.

While interconnectivity is generally recognised as a necessary characteristic of PI, another important consensus about PI is connecting smart standardised containers, which act as the operating unit in logistics operations. Kubek and Więcek (2019) assume PI containers can share real-time information in their conceptual model. In the design of IoPL derived from PI by Pal and Kant (2019), no interconnectivity functions are defined for containers but are related to cargo status sensing. In the blockchain application by Meyer *et al.* (2019), PI containers are modelled as tokens to sense and store data that are manipulated by PI movers, the same as in Hasan *et al.* (2021). In the design of the PI seaport in Fahim *et al.* (2021b), although the composition/decomposition of PI containers is allowed, the containers can only perform data sensing and sharing functions.

Whereas, a tendency of decentralisation can also be observed in the design of PI containers in various studies. Sallez *et al.* (2016) grant class 3 intelligence to the PI containers that allow them to make decisions on their own, like to interact and group in holons. A simulation in a rail-road PI hub shows that evacuation time is significantly lowered with the holonic paradigm. Wang *et al.* (2016) propose the concept of initiative scheduling, allowing decentralised decision-making by machines. It is in comparison with passive scheduling, where the schedule is made by a command centre. In 2016, when IoT devices on PI containers was yet a consensus, Zhang *et al.* (2016) assume smart radio-frequency identification (RFID) tags on smart boxes to achieve the capabilities of “identification, integrity, monitoring, tracking, traceability and location”. The acquired data is processed on a cloud platform for optimisation purposes. Tran-Dang and Kim (2018) consider smart PI containers as smart IoT objects, with basic capabilities like “identification, ambient sensing, computation and communication”. Their design is further elaborated in Tran-Dang *et al.* (2020b), in which a prototype structure for the smart object is defined to be composed of the power module, data acquisition module, processing module and connectivity module. Pan *et al.* (2019) envision PI containers to have class 3 intelligence in the future smart PSS system because this is believed to have better scalability in the long term.

The decentralisation nature of PI is also reflected by the distributed intelligence in other components. It is obvious that blockchain architecture finds synergy therein. Meyer *et al.* (2019) propose PI movers as lightweight nodes, PI nodes storing full blockchain and their belonging

organisations mining new blocks. Tran-Dang *et al.* (2020b) envision employing IoT devices to turn PI movers and PI containers into smart objects with the aforementioned three classes of intelligence and an additional self-organising capability.

In summary, interconnectivity is the foremost and fundamental feature of PI information systems. Based on that, decentralisation in PI is acknowledged and considered especially in terms of connecting PI containers and designing a smart information system. Possible reasons are (i) a full-scale PI network is not designed to be owned by any party. DI has no single owner, thus its derivative PI (Dong and Franklin, 2021); (ii) recent development of IoT devices and ICTs enables a higher level of intelligence; (iii) trust is increasingly an issue that hinders close collaboration, and decentralisation helps to overcome this issue by divide ownership and eliminating monopoly (Meyer *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, there are both intrinsic and extrinsic reasons for researchers of PI to think of decentralisation.

3.3. COMPARING TO CONVENTIONAL LOGISTICS INFORMATION SYSTEM

ICT has been viewed as an essential part of supply chain management for a long time (Gunasekaran and Ngai, 2004). It is well-recognised that ICTs improve logistic efficiency and sustainability by enabling real-time information, integration, collaborative planning, process automation, etc. While distinguishing the trends in PI, we also explore the corresponding trends in conventional logistics research and make comparisons.

PI containers differ from ordinary containers mainly in intelligence and design of size, in which intelligence is more related to logistics information systems. In fact, smart containers are also a focus of researchers outside the context of PI. Ngai *et al.* (2007) propose a system architecture for a container depot, where containers are equipped with RFID tags for identification, positioning, notification and other track and trace functions. For similar usage of RFID tags, David *et al.* (2015) present an architecture based on more recent technologies of IoT and cloud computing for container shipping. They also suggest Sigfox and GPRS networks for data transmission. In an overview of IoT and smart logistics conducted by Ding *et al.* (2021), the impacts of IoT on freight transportation are summarised, which are mainly passive to semi-passive functions (Zou *et al.*, 2014). On the other hand, in many papers about PI, as mentioned in the previous subsection, IoT devices also mainly serve these functions. It is not surprising to see the similarities because the needs for visibility, traceability and collaboration are common, but smart containers in PI seem to have a higher potential for intelligence and can perform more functions in a distributed way. For example, the self-organising holon architecture in Sallez *et al.* (2016) and class 3 intelligence PI containers in the smart PSS system (Pan *et al.*, 2019). PI creates more use cases and encourages researchers to make bold assumptions on logistics information architecture design.

PSS and SoA are also found to be common focuses for information system design. The development of ICTs enables more and more parties to be connected to form a logistic network, and IoT devices exploit more services to offer. There are thus much more resources to be utilised flexibly. As pointed out by Zhang *et al.* (2016), sharing is an important feature of PSS, which is also the emphasis of recent logistics research. In the IoT-enabled SHIP devised by Qiu *et al.* (2015), the outcome is viewed as a PSS that makes decisions based on the shared information from IoT devices. Pan *et al.* (2019) also argue the importance of integrated solutions and introduce smart PSS in PI. This is in line with the spirit of Logistics as a Service (LaaS), resembling the Supply Chain as a Service in Leukel *et al.* (2011) but relies on cooperation among the logistic service providers (LSPs). Multimodal transport also shares the same features to some extent. A concept called a-modal booking (Tavasszy *et al.*, 2015) transfers the work of specifying transport modes from shippers to LSPs. Singh (2014) develops an information system in the principle of SoA to facilitate the synchromodal transport needs among LSPs. But the research is not flourishing. While Pfoser *et al.* (2022) identify many antecedents like real-time switching of mode, cooperative planning, pricing, they are in essence value-adding services provided by a synchronised system. Whereas, PSS and SoA is not concluded as a major trend in many review papers on multimodal transport (Stadieseifi *et al.*, 2014; Giusti *et al.*, 2019; Pfoser *et al.*, 2022). PSS with SoA is thus more stressed in PI and believed to be a future trend for logistics evolution, which should be based on an overarching information system.

While the importance of sharing is stressed, mistrust is becoming an inevitable issue to overcome. Trust is a crucial enabler for collaboration (Fawcett *et al.*, 2012), and its resistance effect on open data sharing has been observed (Prandtstetter *et al.*, 2016). While PI researchers are developing blockchain solutions as a treatment (Betti *et al.*, 2019; Meyer *et al.*, 2019; Hasan *et al.*, 2021), we also found that blockchain has become an even more popular topic without the decentralisation settings provided by PI. Casado-Vara *et al.* (2019) proposed a layered architecture prototype for logistics based on IoT devices and smart contracts. The logistic process is automated by blockchain and intelligent agents. Kshetri (2018) evaluates how blockchain fits supply chain management goals from a theoretical point of view. Tijan *et al.* (2019) review blockchain applications in the logistics sector. They agree with the potential and benefits of blockchain, e.g., transparent ledger for traceability of data, decentralised organisation for peer-to-peer trading, and security through encryption. But they also admit that it is a complex system for companies to implement, and also the scalability issue. In addition, it should be noted that simply implementing blockchain does not convert a logistic model to PI although the interconnectivity and decentralisation features are similar, because in PI, all the efforts serve the principal purpose that cargoes should be encapsulated and transported as how data is processed in DI.

3.4. GAPS AND FUTURE TRENDS

To answer RQ3, we will first identify the popular and emerging technologies and technologies that are studied in the PI papers. These lead to the discussion of the aspects that are not sufficiently researched, problems and the potential for future research.

Cortes-Murcia *et al.* (2022) summarise seven disruptive technologies for the digital interconnection of supply chain management, including blockchain, cloud computing (CC), cyber-physical systems (CPS), IoT, big data analysis (BDA), artificial intelligence (AI) and autonomous vehicles (AV). Their appearance frequency in the reviewed papers is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Frequency of new technologies found in reviewed papers

As shown in Figure 3, IoT is the most agreed upon and indispensable technology for building PI information systems. It fits almost every case to create the link between the physical world and its digital twin or convert things to smart objects. In contrast, no paper includes AV in the research scope. Possible reasons are that AV is too futuristic to be widely applied, and is less related to information system design at the current stage, but more to finding practical use cases.

CC and blockchain are found to be mutually exclusive topics except for the review papers. Their features seem to be completely different. CC has a tendency to centralise computing. It offers flexible and scalable IT services with low implementation costs (Subramanian *et al.*, 2014). In comparison, blockchain is towards decentralisation, whose scalability and complexity are obvious drawbacks (Meyer *et al.*, 2019). Besides, the current research on blockchain in PI information systems still remains in the feasibility justification stage. More complicated structures based on blockchain that are able to provide micro-services are yet to be devised,

where CC can be useful. There are already initial insights (Gai *et al.*, 2020; Fu *et al.*, 2021), implying further research value.

Four out of five pieces of literature refer to BDA as a theoretical solution. Researchers value the visibility provided by BDA, but few of them specify the usage of BDA and its integration into information systems. Moreover, BDA is only mentioned along with IoT, as IoT is viewed as the essential data input.

Only a few papers are found to be based on CPS and AI. CPS is an emerging method to facilitate industrial automation. It integrates computation capabilities into smart devices in the physical world to facilitate interactions and automated operations (Leitão *et al.*, 2016). CPS can accommodate logistic services in agents and its SoA, where AI can also perform more complicated functions. The corresponding information system, however, needs more complicated reconfiguration and design.

Besides the technological advances, we also explore implications from the literature. The first point is that there are no correlations among the articles, which was already indicated by Ambra *et al.* (2019). The work is independent and diversified rather than building upon each other, even though they are on the same technology or topic.

Another point is trust and blockchain. Mistrust appears to be the bottleneck of collaboration, whereas blockchain seems to be the only solution to mistrust in the PI information system. Moreover, there is little consensus reached regarding the architecture design and other technical specifications. Also, in the current research, blockchain merely serves as a distributed ledger that stores information, while other logistic services remain in conceptual discussions. In addition, although it is acknowledged that decentralisation helps avoid monopoly and create trust in the network (Meyer *et al.*, 2019), blockchain is yet the only proposed architecture solution that addresses this aspect of PI. More designs of decentralised architectures and more applications on a higher level need further research.

Standardisation is also becoming a problem. PI envisions having common data standards for interconnectivity, as too many standards are hard to unify in an overarching system. Gharehgozli *et al.* (2019) conduct literature research and interviews to study the effect of standardisation in European intermodal transportation. The interviewees call for European-level standards to avoid unnecessary operations and connect as many organisations as possible. This is also related to network-level cooperation (level 4), which does not yet exist in the reviewed papers. The initiative is only mentioned once in Kubek and Więcek (2019) to connect independent logistic networks. More efforts should be put into treating the different standards of different networks to realise interconnectivity.

At last, PI information system architecture should be able to play its role in providing services, which still lacks research. The PSS architecture of Zhang *et al.* (2016) contains services such as track & trace, grouping and other optimising functions. Pan *et al.* (2019) suggest converting

logistic processes into a service through a smart and interoperable system as an important future for PI information system design. A good example is the pricing model, which has long been a thorny problem for shared logistic networks. This difficulty is more related to managerial issues than algorithm design. Therefore, the information system can play a key part as a trustworthy platform and make structural changes.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we reviewed journal articles regarding information system design in the context of PI. The research is mainly focused on solution design and conceptual research. PI information system solutions have been developed for various application cases, and we are able to find interdisciplinary studies in many papers.

As a distinctive characteristic of PI, interconnectivity and decentralisation have been identified in the information system design, on which PI containers can have a great effect. The decentralisation also helps distribute intelligence into the components of the system to be connected to the PI information system. However, the existing structures are for a smaller problem scope, while for larger decentralised networks, the research remains conceptual.

Besides, by comparing the trends of information system design of PI with conventional logistics, PI researchers have put more efforts into decentralised intelligence and PSS/SoA. Also, blockchain is researched in a more diversified ways in conventional logistics, while it has become a common and prevalent treatment to mistrust.

At last, promising technologies and future trends are summarised in the PI information system research. We raise a few points for further investigation. (i) researchers should exploit more synergies with the existing paper; (ii) blockchain architecture still needs more studies to conclude a prototype architecture (e.g., backend, consensus method, currency), and there should be more decentralised solutions for the trust issue; (iii) standardisation is causing the problem that it initially aims to solve, because there are too many standards that hinder the openness and integration of networks. More research is needed for inter-network cooperations in the PI framework; (iv) PI information systems can help implement more services through its extensive interconnectivity.

There are a few limitations of this paper. This review only concerns journal papers, so that it might overlook some pilot studies or the latest developments, especially from conferences. Also, as the PI information system research is still timewise immature, the researched topics are somewhat fragmented, which makes it indistinctive to draw conclusions. This calls for further investigations to a more comprehensive extent.

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ANNEXE 1. THE LIST OF REVIEWED PAPERS

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
Qiu <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Sharing inventory space usage uncertainty	Real-time accurate information	A service-oriented information architecture for SHIP	2	Supply Hub	Solution design research	IoT	Standardisation, integration of physical assets and services, as well as the demands
Hofman <i>et al.</i> (2016)	General optimisation problems of innovative logistics	Dynamic configuration of data sharing in a complex environment	Semantic tech requirements and benefits in terms of data sharing	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	Semantic, ontology, cloud solutions	Data sharing among stakeholders, utilisation of standardised containers
Maslarić <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Need for logistics transformation towards Industry 4.0	Whether PI is a potential paradigm for Industry 4.0	Review and analysis of Industry 4.0 and PI	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	Cyber Physical Systems, IoT	Openness, interconnectivity, decentralisation

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
Sallez <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Lack of designs regarding container intelligence	Activeness of PI containers	PI container activeness and a descriptive framework	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research, assessment research	Smart containers	Standardised containers with activeness
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2016)	General operational errors due to poor scheduling	Initiative production scheduling	PI-MS, initiative scheduling frameworks	1	Manufacturing environment	Conceptual research	IoT	Interconnected and interactive planning
Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Lack of green and optimised logistics	Overall architecture to share data, increase loading rate and cut pollution	A platform with optimising algorithms, data standard and architecture	3	Conceptual	Solution design research, assessment research	Cloud computing, product-services system, IoT, SoA	Standardised smart boxes
Zhong <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Lack of cost estimation, timely and precise	Real-time accurate information	Layered model of PIMES with technical specifications	1	Workshop	Solution design research,	RFID	Interconnectivity

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
	information on manufacturing and workers					validation research		
Kant and Pal (2017)	Transporting perishable goods	Foundation of IoPL	A layered architecture	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	IoT	Standardisation and infrastructure, and resource sharing
Zhong <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Visibility of operations	Interconnectivity, data process, standards	Descriptive framework, technical specifications, big data analysis framework	1	Intelligent shop floor	Solution design research	Big Data, IoT, cloud technology	Interconnectivity, activeness
Chen <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Energy waste in production, transportation and	Real-time collection, communication and visualisation of information	System architecture for PI-BIMS	1	Prefabricated construction	Solution design research, validation research	Auto-ID, cloud computing	Interconnectivity

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
	assembly stages							
Lin and Cheng (2018)	Accuracy of product sorting and identification , inventory management and product tracking	Interconnectivity, management system, identification	Validation of implementing a PI system, and a system architecture	1	Manufacturing environment	Validation research	RFID, WSN, cloud computing	Interconnectivity for information sharing and computing
Pal, A. and Kant (2018)	Transporting perishable goods	Centralised interconnectivity of the fresh food supply chain	Envisions of infrastructure and technologies for fresh food supply chains	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	IoT, connectivity techs like Bluetooth and NFC	Interconnectivity
Pujo and Ounnar (2018)	Better utilisation of logistics resources	Interconnectivity and collaboration	Holonic paradigm	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	CPS, IoT	Interconnectivity, PI movers, PI containers

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
Tran-Dang and Kim (2018)	General problems in logistics	Apply IoT to the PI system	An information framework and an SoA with IoT	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	IoT, RFID, WSN and other identifying and sensing techs, cloud computing	In line with the foundation by Montreuil <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Betti <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Mistrust in supply chain logistics	Integration of various technologies into an open and trustworthy system	An proof-of-concept and evaluation of blockchain in PI in a simulation	3	Conceptual	Assessment research	Blockchain, IoT	Hyperconnected logistic network. Hubs
Kubek and Więcek (2019)	Negative impact of freight movements in cities	A PI decision-making framework for City Logistics	A multilayer PI decision-making framework for City Logistics	3	City Logistics	Conceptual research	RFID, AI, big data, IoT, connectivity techs like Bluetooth	A hyperconnected logistics network, interoperability among networks, smart standardised containers

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
Meyer <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Sustainability	Transformation towards a decentralised structure	A blockchain-based conceptual framework	3	Conceptual	Conceptual research, solution design research, assessment research	Blockchain, IoT	decentralisation, In line with the foundation by Montreuil <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Pal and Kant (2019)	Transporting perishable goods	An interconnected, smart and automated logistic system	A systematic and layered Internet architecture and an assessment	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research, assessment research	RFID, connectivity techs like Bluetooth	Interconnectivity and standardisation
Pan <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Increasingly complex customer demands	Smart Product-Service System in PI	Key design issues and innovative business models for smart PSS	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	IoT, product-service system, SoA	In line with the foundation by Montreuil

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
Tran-Dang <i>et al.</i> (2020)	-	-	Review the SOTA applications of IoT for logistics	0	Conceptual	Literature research	IoT, cloud computing, big data analysis	Innovation potential, interconnectivity
Tran-Dang <i>et al.</i> (2020b)	General	Application of IoT in PI	Proposing a PI-IoT ecosystem, prototype structures of PI	0	Conceptual	Solution design research	IoT, connectivity technologies, SoA, cloud computing, big data analysis	Interconnectivity, open and shared feature, and other settings in line with Montreuil <i>et al.</i> (2010)
Fahim <i>et al.</i> (2021a)	Vulnerability and lack of resilience	Demonstrate the position and role of maritime ports in PI	Managerial implications and challenges	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	Blockchain, IoT	Openness, standardisation, digitisation
Fahim <i>et al.</i> (2021b)	Dynamic decisions to split and bundle cargo	Track and track capability in seaports	An information architecture for PI seaport with	1	Sea Port	Solution design research	Smart tags (e.g., RFID), smart sensors	Standardised containers, composition & re-composition,

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
			detailed diagrams in layers					interconnectivity, hubs
Hasan <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Efficiency and trust in supply chain	Applying blockchain to PI	Blockchain architectures	0	Conceptual	Solution design research	Blockchain, IoT	Interconnectivity, smart containers, nodes and movers, decentralisation
Tran-Dang and Kim (2021)	-	-	Insights into digital transformation and its effects on PI	0	Conceptual	Conceptual research	IoT, AI, Blockchain, BDA, CC, DT, CPS	Interconnectivity, interoperability, digitisation, containers, nodes and hubs
Tan <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Dynamic allocation and pricing process in parking spaces	Real-time information, truthful pricing and allocation	PI-enabled parking management system and a pricing model	1	Parking spaces	Solution design research, assessment research	IoT (e.g., ultrasonic sensors, RFID)	Interconnectivity

Article Reference	Practical Problem	Conceptual Problem	Outcome/ Contribution	Problem Scope	Application Theme	Research Type	Enabling Technologies	Understanding of PI
Gumzej (2022)	Efficiency, security and sustainability	Smart management in supply chain and logistics	iLS models and ontology in PI context	3	e-commerce	Solution design research	iLS, RFID, GPS, big data analysis	Interconnectivity, decentralisation
Leung <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Improving warehouse processing efficiency for city logistics	Applying the idea of PI hub to traditional warehouses	A digital-twin-based inbound synchronisation framework	1	Warehouse	Solution design research	IoT, DT	Standardisation containers, interconnectivity, interoperability